

THE ROLE OF PHRASEOLOGY IN INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7932247>

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Abstract.

Teaching intercultural communication and the role that the study of phraseology plays in this process. Phraseological units as one of the means of interaction between language and culture. Phraseological units as extra-linguistic realities of the surrounding reality. The purpose of this article is to design a new multi-vector module for working with English communicative (or proverbial) phraseology, designed to modulate the socio-cultural competence of the target audience. Research material: communicative (or proverbial) phraseology of modern English. Methods: theoretical analysis of new pedagogical ideas, studying the products of students' activities, critical analysis of working programs in linguodidactics.

Key words.

phraseosemantic field, phraseological units, lexico-semantic field, lexical units, semantic group, national and cultural originality, verbal comprehension of the world, proverbial.

In accordance with the concept of modernization of Uzbek education, the main goal of modern vocational education is to train a qualified specialist with a given level and profile, able to compete in the labor market, "competent, responsible, fluent in their profession and oriented in related fields of activity, capable of effective work in their specialty at the level of world standards, ready for permanent professional development". growth, social and professional mobility" [1, p. 57].

Here we cannot disagree with the statement that "the development of the system of professional social education, whose graduates are the main agents of changes in the social policy of the Uzbek state, is associated with the development of a competence-approach in their training" [2, p. 311]. This idea, in turn, is closely related to the ideas of the model of education aimed at the successful functioning of the subject of learning [3, p. 272].

According to the Russian expert M. P. Trofimova, the methodological basis of modern education, including higher professional education, is the competence approach programmed by modern regulatory documents [4]. It should be recalled that the concept of intercultural communication began to be actively used about two decades ago in the works of P. P. Borisov, I. A. Zimnaya, S. E. Shishov and others.

S.E. Shishov's Pedagogical School asserts that "intercultural communication is a general ability based on knowledge, experience, values, inclinations acquired through learning," emphasizing that the concept of competence is related to the space of skills, not knowledge [5]. A.K. Markova (1996), N.N. Surtayeva (1997), Z.I. Kolycheva (2003), N.V. Chekaleva (2003), N.F. Radionova (2005), V.A. Bodrov (2006), O.I. Kolycheva (2003), N.V. Chekaleva (2003), N.F. Radionova (2005), O.V. Akulova (2007), G.A. Bordovsky (2007), A.P. Tryapitsyna (2009), V.A. Adolf (2012) and others. With the communicative approach, attention is focused on the result of education, but the result, unlike the traditional approach, is understood not as the sum of learned information, but as the ability to act in various, including problematic and non-standard, situations [4]. Ultimately, the competence approach focuses on increasing the competitiveness of future specialists in the labor market [6].

We consider it necessary to note that the term "intercultural communication", as well as the term "cultural code", is boldly included in the metalanguage of such sciences as linguistics, pedagogy, sociology, cultural studies, and acquires the status of one of the most frequent scientific terms in professional and methodological literature [7, p.178]. As for the methodology and theory and practice of competence approach, these aspects of the problem under consideration are described in considerable detail in numerous works of such foreign scientists as R. Boytsis, J. Raven, L. Holmes, R. White, as well as domestic ones: V. I. Baydenko, I. A. Zimnyaya, A.V. Khutorskoy and others. etc.

Even a cursory acquaintance with the interpretations of competence in the works of these authors makes it obvious that they are extremely diverse, which makes it difficult to develop effective modules for instilling socio-cultural competence in a general methodological direction at various levels of language and specialized education of students.

Although competence is often understood only as the sum of acquired knowledge, we assume that in the definition of this term they do not play a leading role, since the decisive component of any competence is the skills and abilities in applying this knowledge. An essential component of competence is also its

inseparability from the inherent readiness to resolve various controversial issues and debatable problems in the field of mutual understanding and support based on the relevant moral qualities of the student. Here it is appropriate to agree with V. V. Shcherbakova that "knowledge, skills and abilities do not become goals, but means that are constantly improved as the cycles of professional activity repeat, the number of which determines the level of competence formation, which in turn is reflected in the degree of mastering the action" [8].

Didactic experience shows that a practical teacher should focus on the interdisciplinary nature of competence formation, when competence as a whole is understood as the overall quality of a person. On the other hand, the formation of competence is carried out in the process of training in the chosen specialty, which is designed to ensure not only building a successful career, but also fruitful personal and social activities of a specialist.

We agree with the statement of V. A. Degterev and I. A. Larionova that " the competence approach is an approach that focuses on the result of education, and the result is considered not the amount of information learned, but the ability of a person to act in conditions of uncertainty, i.e. in non-standard situations (our italics are T. F.)." the profile of a particular vocational education institution determines the range and structure of these situations.

So, in understanding the competence approach, we consider it important to recognize the importance of educational baggage outside the space of the education system and the conjugation of background knowledge, skills and abilities with the mandatory mastery of a number of competencies.

In this regard, the role of communicative or proverbial phraseology in the formation of socio-cultural competence is immeasurably large due to its value orientations. Proverbs, without any doubt, are a thesaurus of moral ideals, adjusted by socio-cultural development, practical lessons learned from the life of many generations. Thanks to the system of values acquired and fixed in the mind and experience by empirical means, a person perceives the world around him, makes one or another choice and performs actions.

The predominant group of English communicative phraseology consists of proverbial phraseological units that express social and moral values, that is, values that regulate relations between people (Kinsman helps kinsman, but woe to him that has nothing; A near neighbor is better than a far-dwelling kinsman; Wherever you see your kindred, make much of your friends), namely:

a) duty, responsibility: Let every pedlar carry his own burden; Everybody's business is nobody's business; Corporations have neither bodies to be punished nor

souls to be damned; A pot that belongs to many is ill stirred and worse boiled; He who excuses himself, accuses himself;

b) honor: Great honours are great burdens; Honour and ease are seldom bedfellows; Who that in youth no virtue uses, in age all honour him refuses; Honour buys no beef in the market; It is a worthier thing to deserve honour than to possess it;

c) virtue: Virtue is more important than blood; Good is to be sought out and evil attended; Virtue and happiness are mother and daughter; Praise is the reflection of virtue; He that sows virtue, reaps fame;

d) hard work: Diligence is the mother of good fortune; A diligent scholar and the master's paid; The diligent spinner has a large shift; Keep your shop and your shop will keep you; He that labours and thrives, spins gold;

e) willingness to help, generosity: Give and spend and God will send; The hand that gives, gathers; The charitable give out at the door and God puts in at the window; One cannot help many, but many can help one; One good turn deserves another;

f) respect for other people's customs, tolerance: Patience is a flower that grows not in every one's garden; Patient men win the day; The world is for him who has patience; Patience is the best buckler against affronts;

g) hospitality: Good will and welcome is your best cheer; Do not wear out your welcome; It is a sin against hospitality to open your doors and shut up your countenance; If a man receives no guest at home, when abroad he'll have no host; Welcome is the best dish.

Proverbial phraseology gives a fairly complete picture of the moral perfection that a native speaker strives for. Proverbs serve to reinforce such universal ideals, as:

a) patriotism: One Englishman can beat three Frenchmen; Blessed is the eye, that is betwixt Severn and Wye; When a man is tired of London, he is tired of life; A gentleman ought to travel abroad, but dwell at home;

b) the pursuit of knowledge: He that nothing questions, nothing learns; Learning makes a good man better and an ill man worse; Knowledge is the mother of all virtue; Learning is a treasure that accompanies its owner everywhere; Knowledge is no burden;

c) friendship: A good friend is my nearest relation; At marriages and funerals, friends are discerned from kinsfolk; Real friendship does not freeze in winter; Old acquaintance will soon be remembered; Friendship, the older it grows, the stronger it is;

d) integrity: Honesty is the best policy; Cheats never prosper; Honesty may be dear bought, but can never be an ill pennyworth; Honesty is praised and starves; An honest look covers many faults; A man never surfeits of too much honesty;

д) смелость: A brave man may fall, but he cannot yield; A man of courage never wants weapons; None but the brave deserves the fair; The weapon of the brave is his heart; Bold men have generous hearts.

Developing the author's conceptual model of teaching English to students of sociology, we rely on the concept of the activity approach of A. A. Leontiev and the theory of step-by-step formation of mental actions by P. Ya. Galperin, as well as on the linguodidactic works of their followers [9; 10].

The work on the formation of students' socio-cultural competence by means of communicative and proverbial phraseology of the foreign language being studied is based on several directions. First, the English language work program is structured in such a way that each lesson on speech practice begins with students' listening comprehension of a number of proverbial synonyms, consisting of three to five proverbs of modern English, united by one common topic that usually corresponds to the topic of the work program, for example:

Row 1: Necessity is the mother of invention;

Need makes the old wife trot;

Hunger breaks stones walls.

Row 2: An ounce of prevention is better than a pound of cure;

Precaution is better than repentance;

A remedy is worse than disease.

Row 3: Sticks and stones will break my bones, but names will never hurt me;

Words may pass, but blows fall heavy;

Hard words break no bones.

At each lesson, the teacher verbally presents students with a series of synonyms corresponding to the topic being studied, accompanied by speech in a video sequence or without it. The task of students during this semantic warm-up is to give a brief written definition, or interpretation, of the synonymous series of phraseological units-proverbs presented for this case, such as: a) for row 1 - Needs must when the devil drives; b) for row 2 - A stitch in time serves nine; c) for row 3 - Deeds, not words.

When performing this task, students try to follow the requirements for the text of their interpretation from the point of view of authenticity and lack of coincidence with other unsubstantial phraseological units of this series. Students are then asked to illustrate the use of the proverb in a dialogic or monologue format.

The next stage of the module of work on fixing in memory the proverbial proverbs and their cultural and moral rules includes an algorithm of tasks for the SRS to identify and structure (in writing) the thematic and paradigmatic fields formed by the studied proverbs:

a) make a selection of synonyms for the given proverb: If wishes were horses, beggars might ride; (key: If ifs and ands were pots and pans; If my aunt had been a man, she'd have been my uncle; If the sky falls, we shall catchlarks);

b) make a selection of a number of antonyms for a given proverb: Fortune favors the brave (key: Fortune favours fools; God sends fortune to fools);

c) make a selection of thematic series the "Gratitude" theme series to a given proverb: Gratitude preserves old friendships and procures new (key: To a grateful man, give money when he asks; Never look a gift horse in the mouth; Throw no gift again at the giver's head; Half a loaf is better than no bread; Better a lean jade than an empty halter; A crust is better than no bread; Gratitude is the least of virtues, but ingratitude is the worst of vices).

In the third semester, modules for working with non-grammatical phraseological units are complicated by tasks related to the design of their thematic headings. So, for example, in a set of proverbs (100 units) related to the topic "Foolishness", students were able to identify about a dozen thematic subgroups:

1. advantages of stupidity: Fortune favors fools; Children and fools have merry lives;
2. danger of stupidity: Take heed of mad fools in a narrow place.
3. reasons for stupidity: Too much money makes one mad;
4. ineradicable stupidity: He that is born a fool is never cured.
5. the universality of stupidity: Who has neither fools nor beggars nor whores among his kindred, was born of a stroke of thunder;
6. the actions of fools: He is a fool who makes his physician a heir;
7. traits of fools: A fool's bolt is soon shot. Etc.

It should be noted that tasks related to the search for paradigmatic fields of PHE-proverbs, with various kinds of their rubrications, are the most attractive for students, stimulating their interest in the semantics of language units, and in their cultural and moral content.

Semantization of proverbial phraseology by comparing its component composition with socially determined meaning helps students to assimilate socially relevant information about the attitude of English as native speakers to the following aspects of their life: a) to national characteristics: A right Englishmen knows not when a thing is well; The English are the swearing nation; What

Lancashire thinks today, all England will think tomorrow; б) к родственным связям: A man cannot bear all his kin on his back; Kinsman helps kinsman, but woe to him that has nothing; Blood is thicker than water; в) к социальному положению: Bear wealth, poverty will bear itself; Better be envied than pitied; Nothing is to be got without pains except poverty; г) to worldly wisdom: What is not wisdom is danger; Without wisdom wealth is worthless; A wise man never wants a weapon.

Based on the analysis of the experience of teaching foreign language students to sociologists, we are convinced of the validity of the hypothesis that modeling the social and cultural competencies of a student is based not only on the knowledge they receive, but also includes the following components: a) the formation of socially significant qualities in a student: a sense of duty, tolerance, responsiveness, mercy, compassion, faith in good start of a person, hard work, willingness to help; b) programming a social position, developing responsibility, initiative, etc.; c) designing interpersonal communication skills, adequate and active behavior.

As a result of the analysis of two years of experience in teaching English as a foreign language, we find out that the organization of step work from the phrasal definition of proverbial phraseology to the analysis of the paradigmatic space of proverbs creates favorable conditions for modeling the socio-cultural competence of students and the formation of such personality qualities as sociability, friendliness, trust, frankness, hospitality, emotionality, as evidenced by the results of regular tests.

Conclusions. For the most part, the moral and ethical values proclaimed by communicative or proverbial phraseological units are universal, which ensures the universal nature of their socio-cultural potential and its educational impact.

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